

Synthesis and reactivity of triphenyltin(IV) compounds containing Sn-S bonds

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Triphenyltin(IV) compounds containing Sn-S bonds of the general formula $[(C_6H_5)_3SnS(S)POGO]$ ($G = -CH_2\overset{|}{C}(H)-CH_3$, $-CH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2-$ and $-(CH_3)_2C.C(CH_3)_2-$) have been prepared by the reaction of $(C_6H_5)_3SnCl$ and the corresponding NH_4 salt of O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphate in anhydrous benzene. Their bimetallic complexes with Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ag^I have also been synthesised. The bimetallic derivatives are formed through the coordination of the sulfur atom of triphenyltin O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphate to the soft metal acceptor.

The donor abilities of metal dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate towards soft Lewis acid have been little explored^{1,2}. In continuation of our studies on synthesis and reactivity of organomercury O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphates as Lewis base³ and acid⁴, we report here the synthesis, characterisation and reactivity of some triphenyltin(IV) O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphates toward soft metal acceptors such as Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ag^I .

Results and Discussion

The interaction of triphenyltin chloride with ammonium salt of O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphate in (1 : 1 molar ratio) in anhydrous benzene yields the desired product,

The 1 : 1 adducts of triphenyltin- O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphate with soft Lewis acceptors such as Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ag^I have been obtained by stirring a mixture of the two components in acetone at room temperature,

LA = $HgCl_2$, $Hg(SCN)_2$, $Hg(OCOCF_3)_2$, $CdCl_2$, $AgSCN$, $AgOCOCF_3$

The physical data of the triphenyltin O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphate indicate 1 : 1 $[(C_6H_5)_3Sn : \text{dithiophosphate}]$ stoichiometry. The products are crystalline, white to cream solids, stable at room temperature and are insensitive to atmospheric oxygen and moisture. They are soluble in common organic solvents.

The analytical data for the molecular adducts (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 1 (donor : acceptor) stoichiometry. They are solid, stable to ambient temperature and insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMSO.

The molar conductance data ($\sim 4.0 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of triphenyltin- O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphates and their molecular adducts in DMSO show their non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectra : IR bands are observed at 1070 ± 2 $[P-O-C]$ and $851 \pm 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ $[(P)-O-C]$. The bands at 703 ± 1 ($P=S$) and $540 \pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($P-S$) invariably indicates the presence of unidentate dithiophosphate group bonded to triphenyltin moiety⁵⁻⁷. The weak intensity bands are observed at 410 ($Sn-S$) and $265 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($Sn-Ph$)⁸.

In the IR spectra of the bimetallic complexes triphenyltin O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphate. $M''X_2$ or $M'X$ ($M' = Ag$; $M'' = Hg, Cd$; $X = Cl, SCN$ or $OCOCF_3$), the $\nu_{P=S}$ band shows a negative shift ($685 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The band at $540 \pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($P-S$) indicates the presence of unidentate O,O' -alkylene dithiophosphate group. The two bands associated with $\nu_{(P)-O-C}$ and ν_{P-O-C} appear at 1080 ± 4 and $860 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

The considerable lowering of $\nu_{P=S}$ band indicates coordination of the sulfur atom of the ligand to soft metal acceptor. There is a shift of electron density from oxygen through phosphorus and sulfur to the soft metal acceptor³. A small positive shift in $\nu_{(P)-O-C}$ ($1080 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and ν_{P-O-C} (860

Table 1. Analytical data of $[(C_6H_5)_3SnS(S)POGO].M'X$ or $M''X_2^*$

$M'X / M''X_2$	$G = -CH_2\overset{\downarrow}{C}(H)-CH_3$		$G = -(CH_3)_2C.C(CH_3)_2-$		$G = -CH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2-$	
	Colour	Decomp. pt. °C	Colour	Decomp. pt. °C	Colour	Decomp. pt. °C
AgSCN	Brown	190	Yellow	204	Cream	198
AgOCOCF ₃	Brown	204	Ash	184	Ash	188
Hg(OCOCF ₃) ₂	White	194	White	220	Yellow	205
Hg(SCN) ₂	White	215	Green	202	Green	198
HgCl ₂	White	210	Ash	190	Yellow	202
CdCl ₂	Brown	230	Green	212	Yellow	230
	Yields 62–76%		Yields 60–70%		Yields 68–75%	

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

$\pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) also indicates that on coordination from sulfur to the soft metal acceptors, the considerable shift of electron density increases the bond order of the C–O and P–O bond³. The band at 410 ± 2 (Sn–S) and $266 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Sn–Ph) remain unaffected in the spectra of the molecular adducts.

The trifluoroacetate groups are unidentate⁹ since $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ appear at 1690 ± 5 and $1420 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively with $-\Delta \text{OCO} = 270 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thiocyanate group is S-bonded since $\nu_{C\equiv N}$, $\nu_{C=S}$ and ν_{SCN} bands appears at ~ 2080 , ~ 720 and $\sim 480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively¹⁰. Absorption due to $M''\text{-Cl}$ stretching modes could not be identified as they lie beyond the recorded range of spectra.

It is thus observed that one of the sulfur atoms of the dithiophosphate group in $[Ph_3SnS(S)POGO]$ is coordinated to a soft metal atom giving rise to bimetallic dithiophosphates.

¹H NMR spectra : In the ¹H NMR spectra of $[(C_6H_5)_3SnS(S)PO(CH_3)_2C.C.(CH_3)_2O]$ the C_6H_5 -Sn and CH_3 signals appear at δ 8.4–7.51 (m) and 1.55 (s), respectively, whereas in case of $[(C_6H_5)_3SnS(S)POCH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2O]$, the C_6H_5 -Sn, O-CH₂ and CH₂ signals appear at δ 8.2–7.3 (m), 4.08–4.06 (m) and 3.56–3.42 (m), respectively. In the spectra of $[(C_6H_5)_3SnS(S)PO(CH_3)_2C.C.(CH_3)_2O]$, Hg (OCOCF₃)₂, C_6H_5 -Sn signals appear at δ 8.26–7.32 (m), whereas there is slight low-field shift in CH₃ protons which appear at δ 1.58 (s). The low field shift in CH₃ signals in molecular adduct indicates considerable shift of electron density from oxygen to the metal atom through sulfur³.

Thus, on the basis of these results and support from the previous work¹¹, a tetrahedral structure containing a unidentate dithiophosphate group and a four-coordinated tin atom¹² may be assigned to triphenyltin *O,O'*-alkylene

dithiophosphate complex. Moreover, in case of molecular adducts, it is assumed that two molecules of metal acceptors bind to two different sulfur atoms. The dithiophosphate group thus acts as a bridge between triphenyltin and soft metal^{1,3}. In these molecular adducts, Hg^{II} and Cd^{II} are tricoordinated^{13,14} and Ag^I is dicoordinated¹⁵.

Experimental

Triphenyltin chloride was prepared by reported method¹⁶. Solvents were dried and purified by standard procedures. *O,O'*-Alkylene dithiophosphoric acid and their ammonium salts were prepared according to the reported procedures^{6,7}. Molar conductance (in DMSO) was measured using a dip-type conductivity cell on a Decible DC 610 conductivity meter. Metal and sulfur were determined¹⁷. IR spectra (KBr/CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer, FTIR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1800 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Bruker WM-400 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Reaction of $(C_6H_5)_3SnCl$ and $NH_4S(S)PO(CH_3)_2C.C.(CH_3)_2O$: A mixture of triphenyltin chloride (3.36 g, 0.01 mol) and ammonium *O,O'*-tetramethylethylene dithiophosphate (2.28 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous benzene was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the compound precipitated by the addition of pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°). The precipitate was washed with pet. ether and diethyl ether, and dried over P₂O₅ under reduced pressure.

The reaction of $(C_6H_5)_3SnCl$ with $NH_4S(S)POCH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2O$ and $NH_4S(S)POCH_2C(H)OCH_3$ was carried out similarly. All compound gave satisfactory Sn and S analysis : $[(C_6H_5)_3SnS(S)POGO]$, where $G = -CH_2-CHCH_3$ (85%), 210° d; $G = -CH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2-$ (75%), 115°; $G = -(CH_3)_2C.C(CH_3)_2-$ (78%), 102°.

Reaction of triphenyltin O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphate with Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ag^I salt : In a representative experiment, a solution of triphenyltin O,O'-tetramethylethylene dithiophosphate (0.561 g, 0.001 mol), Hg(OCOFCF₃)₂ (0.426 g, 0.001 mol) in acetone (20 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 4 h. The resulting solid was washed with acetone and diethyl ether, and dried over P₂O₅ under reduced pressure. Similar products were prepared using Hg(SCN)₂, HgCl₂, CdCl₂, AgSCN, AgOCOFCF₃ as acceptors with all triphenyltin O,O'-alkylene dithiophosphates.

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